

PREPARATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE BUCKYPAPER/EXOXY COMPOSITES

L. L. Shen and L. Liu

School of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University
100 Zhangwu Road, Shanghai, China
Email:584658187@qq.com

Keywords: Carbon nanotube, Buckypaper, Mechanical property, Composites

ABSTRACT

In the present study, the carbon nanotube (CNT) buckypapers (BPs) were prepared by positive pressure filtering process and then were infiltrated with epoxy resin by using of improved preparation processing. Tensile properties of standard specimens were measured according to ASTM D638 method. Fractured surfaces of some typical specimens were analysed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Results have shown that the strengths and moduli of the BP/epoxy composites can be improved significantly, an improvement up to 143% and 390% in tensile strength and modulus was obtained compared with neat epoxy resin. Meanwhile, SEM observation showed that the CNTs in the BPs were infiltrated well with epoxy and good interfacial bonding between the CNTs and epoxy was also obtained.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are molecular-scale tubes of graphitic carbon with exceptional physical and mechanical properties, such as exceptionally high elastic modulus, large elastic strain and fracture strain sustaining capability, which are considered as the extremely promising reinforcement materials to be used in high performance structural and multifunctional composites[1]. CNTs are considered to be ideal reinforcing materials for making thermoset composites since CNT/epoxy composites were first fabricated and investigated by Ajayan et al. in 1994 [2]. There are usually two ways to introduce CNTs into epoxy resins, microscopic dispersion and macroscopic assemblies of CNTs into buckypaper based processing [3, 4]. Microscopic dispersion of short CNTs into epoxy to achieve good quality of dispersion and interfacial bonding has been the focal point of many investigations. However, some well-known problems also exist so far. Firstly, the homogenous dispersion of CNTs into epoxy in nano-scale is difficult because micron-sized agglomerates are unavoidable due to high specific surface area of CNTs [4]. Secondly, even at a low concentration (4 wt% or less), the very high surface-to-volume ratio of CNTs make the solution very viscous, which in turn would affect their uniform dispersion, limit their loading in polymer and result more complicated processing [4]. Furthermore, interface between CNTs and epoxy is found to be weak [3]. Therefore, the mechanical and physical properties of CNTs/epoxy composites are much lower than the predicted values and there still needs some efforts to overcome the above mentioned critical issues to fabricate high-quality CNTs/polymer composites with high CNTs loading.

The BPs based processing is a new method to fabricate CNTs/epoxy composites with uniform distribution and a high loading of CNTs [5-9]. Although there are some sporadic pioneer works on study of CNT BP reinforced epoxy composites [5-9], significant mechanical strength enhancement over the neat matrices is rare in the literature [7-9]. To make full reinforcing advantages of CNT BPs, more efforts should be made to find the best preparation process, various mechanical properties and microstructures.

Therefore, the goal of this study is to prepare porous CNT BP/epoxy composites, and to investigate the reinforcing effect of the BPs on the epoxy resin. The BPs were prepared by using positive pressure method, and obtained BPs were infiltrated with resin film by using of resin film infusion (RFI) process. Tensile mechanical properties and corresponding fractured surfaces of the composites were investigated to explore the reinforcing effect and fracture mechanism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Preparation

The multi-wall CNTs (8~15 nm in diameter and 10~30 μm in length) used in this study were purchased from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co., functionalizing with 1.85 wt. % of carboxyl group. The CNTs were obtained as suspension and with a CNTs weight concentration of nearly 2 wt. %. The suspension was filtrated through a membrane with a pore size of 0.8 μm with the aid of compressed air. The compressed air produced positive pressure about 0.02~0.3 MPa and uniformly acted on the solution surface. The BP was formed on the filter membrane. After dried in an oven, the BP was carefully peeled off from the microporous membrane. Then, the obtained BP was treated with heat and nitric acid to remove surfactant. Finally, clean and smooth BP was obtained. The thickness of the prepared BP was about 30-40 μm .

The used epoxy resin film was nearly 20 μm . Single layer and multi-layer of CNT BP/epoxy resin composites were fabricated by using of RFI process. The resin film was stuck on one side of the BP, and then melted 10 min in a hot press under 90 C° to form preform. Some of the preforms were pre-stretched to improve the alignment of CNTs in the composites with an extension of 25% compared with original length of the specimen. Then, the single layer and four layers of the preforms were laid down carefully into the mold of the hot press (showed in Fig. 1) and the temperature were increased to 120 C° and kept for 2h to allow the resin infiltrated the CNT paper well. After that, the temperature were increased to 180 C° and held on 2h. Finally, the temperature was cooled down to room temperature. In the cure process, the applied pressure was 0.7 MPa. Five specimens, neat epoxy, single layer composites with and without pre-stretching, and four layers of composites with and without pre-stretching, were prepared and studied.

Figure 1: Abbreviated drawing of BP/epoxy composites fabrication.

2.2 Characterization

The morphology of the BP was observed with a SEM machine (Philips XL 30 ESEM instrument). Tensile testing of large-size specimens was carried out to examine the tensile properties of the composite laminates. The corresponding specimens were prepared according to ASTM D638 testing standard, with a length of 115 mm and a width in narrow section of 6 mm. The thickness of the specimens was listed in Table 1. The tests were conducted using a universal testing machine (Zwicki-Z2.5, the Zwick/Roell, Germany), with a gauge length of 30 mm and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The number of testing specimens for each case was five. After tests, fractured surfaces of some typical specimens were characterized using a SEM machine (Philips XL 30 ESEM).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology of the BP

Fig. 2 presented the SEM image of the obtained CNT BP. The paper was porous with

relatively large open pores and uniform distribution of the CNTs. The average diameter of the pores was measured as $42\pm 20\text{nm}$ using software of ImageJ, which was beneficial for infiltrating with epoxy resin. Also, the surfaces of the CNTs were clean and smooth, indicating the BP was pure and with no impurities

Figure 2: SEM image of the prepared BP.

3.2 Tensile properties of the composites

Fig.3 gave the tensile stress-strain curves of specimens with and without BPs. It can be seen from Fig.3 that the neat epoxy had relatively lower loading ability and larger fractured elongation compared with the BP reinforced specimens. The calculated strength, modulus and elongation of the specimens were given in Table 1.

For the single layer BP reinforced specimens, the tensile strength, modulus and elongation were 140.0 MPa, 10.96 GPa and 2.47% for the un-treated specimen, and 156.3 MPa, 14.61 GPa and 1.96% for the pre-stretched specimen, respectively. Strengths were increased by 117% and 143%, moduli were improved by 268% and 390%, respectively comparing with neat epoxy resin. While, the elongation of reinforced specimens decreased significantly. By pre-stretching 25%, the alignment of CNTs in the specimen was improved and maybe more CNTs would be aligned along the loading direction. This will help improve the strength and modulus. The strength and modulus of the pre-stretched specimens were improved by 11.6% and 33.3% compared with the un-treated single layer BP reinforced specimen.

Figure.3: The stress-strain curve of neat epoxy and BP/epoxy specimens.

For the four layers of BP/EP composites, gains in strengths and moduli were obtained. But the reinforcing effect was lower than that of the corresponding single layer BP/EP composites. The reason is that thicker specimen may result in poor resin infiltration in the buckypaper mats and poor interfacial bonding may occur. Similarly, lower elongation was obtained for the reinforced specimens. Also, better mechanical properties were achieved for the pre-stretched specimen. Therefore, it can be concluded that the mechanical properties would be improved significantly by pre-stretching the specimens.

Specimens	type	Elongation [%]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]
1	Neat EP	4.60	64.5	2.98
2	1 layer BP/EP	2.47	140.0	10.96
3	1 layer BP/EP*	1.96	156.3	14.61
4	4 layers BP/EP	1.74	123.0	12.74
5	4 layers BP/EP*	1.50	145.5	16.44

Table 1: Tensile properties (* indicating pre-stretched specimens)

3.3 Fractured surfaces

Fig.4 presented the SEM images of the fractured surfaces of specimens of neat epoxy and single layer or multi-layer buckypapers reinforcing epoxy composites. The fractured surface of neat epoxy was rough and had many initial fracture points (Fig.4 a₁). The rough surface and fractured dimples indicated that the epoxy was tough to somewhat, which was coherent with the larger fractured elongation showed in Fig.3. The surface showed smooth in every fractured dimple (Fig.4 a₂).

The fractured surface of the single layer buckypaper reinforced epoxy without pre-stretching (Fig. 4 b₁) was not as rough as that of neat epoxy, but many heaves and wrinkled lines were significant. It means that the CNTs in the composites hindered the propagation of the cracks and the crack would split when it met the CNTs. The whole thickness of the specimen (Fig.4 b₁) was measured as 66 μm by using software ImageJ. There was no resin rich zone on both sides of the specimen, meaning the resin fully penetrated the buckypaper and infiltrated the buckypaper well. With a higher magnification, the fractured surface was rougher than that of neat resin with same magnification (Fig. 4 b₂). It can be seen from Fig. 4 b₂ that the CNTs in the fractured surface were uniformly dispersed. The CNTs were pulled out and broke. The interfacial bonding between CNTs and epoxy was good because no gaps between CNTs and epoxy were visible. For the single layer specimen with pre-stretching, the fractured surface was similar to that of un-treated specimen, with no resin rich zone on both sides. But the fractured surface had more and smaller heaves and wrinkled lines. The thickness was obtained as 56 μm , decreased by 15% compared with the specimen without pre-stretching. This means that the CNTs content in the composite would be improved. The magnified picture zoomed in Fig.4 c₁ was shown in Fig.4 c₂, suggesting more CNTs were visible on the fractured surface and tended to align along the loading direction which resulted in the enhancement of strength and modulus. The fractured surface was also rough enough.

As for the four-layer buckypapers reinforced epoxy composites (Fig.4 d₁ and e₁), the fractured surfaces were similar and small wrinkled lines were the predominant views. There were no resin rich layers between adjacent layers, indicating good infiltration between resin and buckypaper. With pre-stretching, the thickness of the specimen (Fig.4 e₁) decreased by 11% compared with that of the un-treated specimen (Fig.4 d₁). The local region zoomed in Fig.4 d₁ showed that there was lack of resin in some local regions because some pores and gaps occurred on the fractured surface and some CNTs were naked (showed in Fig.4 d₂). Although, the thickness of the pre-stretched specimen decreased, but there were no visible zones lacking of resin and no pores in the fractured surface (Fig. 4 e₂). Therefore, the better microstructure of Fig. 4 e₂ resulted better strength than that of Fig. 4 d₂.

Figure 4: The SEM images of fractured specimens with (a) neat epoxy resin, (b) 1 layer BP/epoxy composite, (c) 1 layer BP/epoxy composite with pre-stretching, (d) 4 layers BP/epoxy composite and (e) 4 layers BP/epoxy composite with pre-stretching, where subscripts 1 and 2 indicate different magnifications.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, single layer or multi-layer CNT buckypaper reinforced epoxy composites were obtained by using of resin film infusion processing. The tensile properties of the composites were improved significantly by introducing the CNT buckypapers, especially for the pre-stretched specimens. For the single layer buckypaper reinforced composites, the strength is improved by 117 and 142.3% for the un-treated composite and pre-stretched composite, respectively. Similarly, increases in modulus rate up to 267.8 and 390.3%, respectively. Additionally, corresponding enhancements in four layers buckypapers reinforced epoxy composites are obtained, respectively for the un-treated and pre-stretched specimens. The pre-stretching has better reinforcing effect. Also, pull-out and breakage of CNTs, increasing interfaces fracture, as well as improved interfacial bonding strength contribute the reinforcing effect. The present study demonstrates that the proposed porous buckypapers not only benefit the infiltration to epoxy resin but also have positive effect on the strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project was supported by the Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 11172211). Support from mechanical properties testing and materials characterization is appreciated. The authors also acknowledge graduate student Yiwen Zhou for useful advice and help.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Wang, R. Liang, B. Wang and C. Zhang. Dispersion and thermal conductivity of carbon nanotube composites, *CARBON*, **47**, 2009, pp. 53–57.
- [2] P.M. Ajayan, O. Stephan, C. Coliex and D. Trauth. Aligned carbon nanotube arrays formed by cutting a polymer resin nanotube composites, *Science*, **265**, 1994, pp. 1212-1214.
- [3] J.N. Coleman, U. Khan, W.J. Blau and Y.K. Gunko. Small but strong: A review of the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube-polymer composites, *CARBON*, **44**, 2006, pp. 1624-1652.
- [4] L.B. Hu, D.S. Hecht and G. Grüner. Carbon nanotube thin films: fabrication, properties, and applications, *Chem Rev*, **110**, 2010, pp. 5790-5884.
- [5] Z. Wang, Z.Y. Liang, B. Wang, C. Zhang and L. Kramer. Processing and property investigation of single-walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) buckypaper/epoxy resin matrix nanocomposites, *Compos Part A: Appl Sci Manuf*, **35**, 2004, pp. 1225-1232.
- [6] Q.F. Cheng, J.P. Wang, K.L. Jiang, Q.Q. Li and S.S. Fan. Fabrication and properties of aligned multiwalled carbon nanotube-reinforced epoxy composites, *J Mater Res*, **23**, 2008, pp. 2975-2983.
- [7] W. Ma, L. Liu, Z. Zhang, R. Yang, G. Liu, T. Zhang, X. An, X. Yi, Y. Ren, Z. Niu, J. Li, H. Dong, W. Zhou, P.M. Ajayan, S. Xie. High-strength composite fibers: realizing true potential of carbon nanotubes in polymer matrix through continuous reticulate architecture and molecular level couplings, *Nano Letters*, **9**, 2009, pp. 2855-2861.
- [8] Q.F. Cheng, J.W. Bao, J.G. Park, Z.Y. Liang, C. Zhang and B. Wang. High mechanical performance composite conductor: multi-walled carbon nanotube sheet/bismaleimide nanocomposites, *Adv Funct Mater*, **19**, 2009, pp. 3219-3125.
- [9] Q.F. Cheng, B. Wang, C. Zhang and Z.Y. Liang. Functionalized carbon-nanotube sheet/bismaleimide nanocomposites: mechanical and electrical performance beyond carbon-fiber composites. *Small*, **6**, 2010, pp. 763-767.